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PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN NORTH MACEDONIA'S LOCAL GOVERNMENT

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of this paper is to identify the current state and efficiency of performance management processes, including evaluation systems in the local self-government organizations in the Republic of North Macedonia and possible improvements that can be incorporated in the future. The primary research in this paper includes a qualitative research of data collected through a questionnaire and interviews with the local public sector officials in North Macedonia. Findings suggest that most Macedonian municipalities are employing public servants based on political party affiliation instead of skills, knowledge and competence. Corruption is well spread and the system is neither nurturing the hard-working employees nor punishing the non-workers. Proposed solutions are: de-partization, digitalisation and higher transparency. The creation of the performance management scheme in the Macedonian municipalities could ultimately improve the productivity of public sector management and significantly improve the functionality of the entire system and quality of national living.

KEY WORDS: performance Management, North Macedonia, human resources, local government and digitalisation

INTRODUCTION

The municipalities as a local government in the country focus on a wide range of areas such as municipal property, urban and spatial management, operation management for inter-municipal activities, as well as strategic operations and organizational management. In North Macedonia, common administration and funding are utilized by various municipalities, with funds transferred from the central budget to local governments (State Department,

2018). This paper aims to identify the performance management practices undertaken by local governments in North Macedonia and assess their effectiveness.

The contribution of this research lies in its focus on the interplay between performance management systems and the challenges posed by political affiliations and corruption in the context of North Macedonia. By exploring these dynamics, this study seeks to fill a gap in the existing literature on public sector management in transitional economies.

The structure of the paper is as follows: the next section provides a comprehensive literature review that contextualizes performance management within local governance. Following that, the methodology section outlines the research design and data collection methods employed in this study. The findings section presents the results of the analysis, while the discussion interprets these results in relation to existing literature. Finally, the conclusion summarizes the key insights and suggests practical recommendations for improving performance management in Macedonian municipalities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance management has been defined by many previous studies and one of the most common and distinguished definitions is the one provided by Aguinis (2019, p.1), stating that performance management is a continuous process of identifying, measuring and developing the performance of individuals and teams and aligning performance with the strategic goals of the organization. As mentioned by Van Dooren, et al., (2015), performance management is a fundamental determinant of quality factors within organisations such as: quality of actions that are performed and quality of achievements that have been achieved from the implemented actions. Amaratunga (2001) defines performance management as a process used to identify, encourage, measure, evaluate, improve and of course reward the performance of employees in an organization. Also, Idemobi, Onyeizugbe and Akpunonu (2011) defined it as a tool that focuses on managing the individual and the work environment in such a way that the individual or team can achieve the set organizational goals. According to Amaratunga et al., (2001), the performance management system implies the use of performance measurement information in effecting positive changes in organizational systems, processes and cultures, through setting

performance goals, prioritizing and allocating resources, confirming or changing managers' policies towards organizational goals and sharing performance results from achieving goals. Additionally, some studies (e.g. Armstrong, 2021; De Waal, 2003; Srbinska, 2019) see performance management as a set of activities designed to develop and manage people in order to improve the achievement of specific short-term goals. Primarily performance management perspectives focus on the specific number of tasks being performed by any performing agent and across different industries within the public sector, this can include activities by a police patrol, medical treatment, court judgments, teachers teaching in a class or vaccination campaign workers. Another perspective of performance management as highlighted in the studies of Amhalhal, et al., (2021) was the agenda perspective in which performance management steps are always classified to be improvement plans or agendas. Many previous researchers have opined that the performance management concepts first emerged when practitioners started talking about the transformation of the performance appraisal from a scheduled event to a dedicated process (Schleicher, et al., 2018, p.18-20). Defining the basis of performance management provides multiple different types of definitions that identify the process as "an integrated approach for individual contributors", "the development process of individuals with commitment and competence", and "managing business" or "the process of directing and supporting employees to work as effectively and efficiently as possible". In general, the main goals of performance management system implementation in the public sector by local governments in countries include the establishment of effective oversight and guidance for managing work done by public servants. According to previous studies, performance management contributes significantly to increasing motivation levels of employees, self-esteem as well as manager insights about their subordinates (Anning,2018).

IMPORTANCE OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT IN ACHIEVING SUCCESS IN LOCAL GOVERNMENT

According to Morgan and Murgatroyd (1994), because public sector businesses mostly provide services rather than manufactured goods, it is challenging to identify a common model of management for them. Nonetheless, since performance management is a consistent and structured approach to determination, evaluation, and enhancement of both personal and institutional performance, as Neely et al. (2006), noticed, the new approach to public management is linked to a rise in demand in performance

management in government organizations. In addition to their thesis, performance management, as a contemporary strategy, is confident in lowering service costs, raising productivity, and boosting engagement in organizations within the public sector. In that manoeuvre, there are several advantages when utilizing performance management in municipalities. Initially, performance management systems make it clear who is in charge of monitoring whether goals are met or not and what the expected results are. Furthermore, the local authorities' aims are the main focus of performance management, which exploits their energy to accomplish them. In order to close gaps in performance in the local government sector, it offers a balanced strategy for tracking and evaluating performance, gaining knowledge, and feedback actions. Rashid's thesis (1999) clearly defines individual, team, and organizational goals, providing organizations with more precise and attainable insights regarding the feasibility of their targets. Moreover, it emphasizes the importance of enabling personnel and councils to make more effective use of their limited resources.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of this paper is to identify the current state and effectiveness of performance management processes, including evaluation systems in the local self-government organizations of the Republic of North Macedonia and possible improvements that can be incorporated in the future.

Following the above structure, this paper as well as the empirical research under it, is founded on the following research hypotheses:

- ✓ H1: Performance management system positively affects effective management in Macedonian local governments. – General hypothesis
- ✓ H2: Municipality budget positively affects performance management in the municipalities in North Macedonia.
- ✓ H3: Digitalisation positively affects performance management in the municipalities in North Macedonia.
- ✓ H4: Transparency positively affects performance management in the municipalities in North Macedonia.

To test the above hypothesis and for the purposes of this paper, electronic survey was conducted on totally 190 respondents, public servants working in the municipalities across the country. The survey was designed to gather data on key variables relevant to the study.

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1. *Performance management System (PM)*: This variable was operationalized through a series of survey questions that assessed the extent to which municipalities have implemented structured performance management practices, including goal setting, performance appraisal and feedback mechanisms.
 2. *Municipality Budget (B)*: Respondents rated the adequacy and allocation of their municipality's budget on a scale from 1 to 5, allowing for a quantitative assessment of how budgetary considerations impact performance management.
 3. *Digitalisation (D)*: This variable was evaluated through survey items that measured the degree of digital tools and technologies adopted in municipal operations, including online services, data management systems and communication platforms.
 4. *Transparency (T)*: Transparency was assessed via questions focused on the availability of information to the public, the clarity of decision-making processes and mechanisms for public accountability.

Demographic data were also collected: 61% are female and 39% are male; 64% work in urban municipalities, whereas 36% come from rural municipalities. Furthermore, 8% of the respondents are employed in the respective municipality with definite status, as opposed to 92% which have permanent employment status. 39% of the respondents have a managerial working position, whereas 61% hold non-managerial roles.

INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

Regarding effective management in the municipalities in North Macedonia, on a scale from 1 to 5, the average level based on the obtained answers, is 3.73, with standard deviation of 0.46, which results with a coefficient of variation of around 12%. The median of effective management is very close to the mean, implying symmetric distribution, which is also visible from the skewness indicator (which is 0), as well as from the boxplot and histogram below. This is confirmed also by the calculated Jarque-Bera statistics of 0,16, and the corresponding p-value of 0.9224, which means that the variable effective management follows normal distribution.

On the other hand, the level of performance management in the municipalities across the country, based on the obtained responses, is assessed slightly lower than the effective management. The average level is

3.2, with standard deviation of 0.36, and coefficient of variation of around 11%, which also indicates stability of the data. Regarding the distribution, performance management variable also follows normal distribution. The skewness is around 0 (specifically 0.26), whereas the kurtosis is 2.76, which results in Jarque-Berra statistics of 2.52 and corresponding p-value of 0.2838.

Regarding the level of digitalisation in the municipalities, out of maximum 5 points, based on the obtained answers, the average level is almost 3.8. The results by participant are stable, with standard deviation of 0.57, and coefficient of variation of 15%. The data under this variable is normally distributed, which means that parametric test can be applied.

Employees in the municipalities in North Macedonia, participants in the conducted survey, rated municipal budget between 1.33 and 4.33 on a scale from 1 to 5, with average level of 3.7. The standard deviation of this variable is 0.58, which is slightly higher compared to performance management, but still stable, with coefficient of variation equal to 16%. Unlike the previous two variables, budget variable does not follow normal distribution, which means that for this variable better measure of central tendency would be the median than the average level.

The same applies to the transparency of the municipalities. Based on the survey results, it ranges between 1.8 and 4.2, with average score of around 3.6. However, the data distribution is not normal (Jarque-Berra statistics of 24.01, with p-value equal to 0), whereby the median value, as a more representative measure of central tendency, is slightly higher (3.8).

Visual representation of the measures of central tendency, mean and median, by model variable. As it can be noticed, participants in the survey rated highest the level of digitalisation in the municipality they work in, as opposed to the level of performance management, which they valued less, compared to the other variables.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics by variable

Indicator	EM	PM	B	D	T
Mean	3.73	3.20	3.70	3.79	3.58
Median	3.75	3.17	3.67	3.86	3.80
Maximum	5.00	4.17	4.33	5.00	4.20
Minimum	2.56	2.33	1.33	2.14	1.80

Std. Dev.	0.46	0.36	0.58	0.57	0.54
Coeff. of Variation	12%	11%	16%	15%	15%
Skewness	0.05	0.26	-1.00	-0.32	-0.87
Kurtosis	3.11	2.76	4.25	3.02	3.20
Jarque-Bera	0.16	2.52	44.30	3.21	24.01
Probability	0.922 4	0.283 8	0.000 0	0.200 7	0.000 0

Figure 1: Measures of central tendency of the model variables

It is presented the box-plots for each variable used in the model. This is basically a visual image of the overall descriptive statistics presented above. Namely, one can see here the average value (black dot); the median value with its confidence interval (black line with blue shaded area); the inter-quartile range, or the middle 50% of the data (white rectangle box); the minimum and maximum values (left and right end of the horizontal line); as well as outliers, positive and negative (circled dots on the far left and far right of the line).

From the figure, it is evident that there is a negative skew in the budget and transparency variables, as observed from the tails on the left side of the respective box blots.

Figure 2: Box-plots of the model variables

Based on the category of respondents, given their demographic characteristics, the analysis revealed that there are no statistically significant differences between mean / median values of the variables for a different category of respondents. This means that on average, all categories of respondents have generally the same perceptions regarding the model variables, regardless of their sex, age, working position, employment status, type of municipality, or working experience.

The only exception pertains to the digitalisation and transparency variables at municipal level. The analysis showed that urban municipalities, on average, have a higher level of transparency compared to the rural ones (3.8 for the urban and 3.4 for rural). Similarly urban municipalities exhibited a higher level of digitalisation (3.93 for the urban, as opposed to 3.56 for the rural municipalities).

Figure 3 below presents the central tendency measures for each variable, by different categories of participants. In line with the established methodology, for the municipal budgets, as well as for the level of transparency, since these variables do not follow normal distribution.

Figure 3: Mean / median responses for each variable, by category of respondents

The analysis conducted in this regard is based on several tests. Since parametric tests consider the mean as a measure of central tendency, whereby normal distribution of the data is assumed, these tests are applied for the normally distributed variables, such as Effective Management, Performance Management, and Digitalisation. For Budget and

Transparency, given their non-normal distribution, non-parametric alternatives considering the median value are applied.

CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS

This study aimed to evaluate the current state and effectiveness of performance management processes within local self-governments in the Republic of North Macedonia. The quantitative analysis conducted, which include regression analysis, descriptive statistics, equality tests and correlation analysis, yielded significant findings.

The results indicate that performance management systems in municipalities positively influence effective management. Specifically, a unit increase in performance management is associated with 0.78-point increase in effective management. These findings highlight the importance of implementing robust performance management frameworks to enhance the operational effectiveness of local governments.

Policy Implementations

The implementation of this research are substantial for policymakers and local government administrators. First, there is a clear need for improved performance management systems that are transparent, digitalized and aligned with strategic goals. By prioritizing these areas, local governments can foster a more accountable and efficient public sector.

Additionally, the results suggest that addressing budgetary constraints and enhancing transparency can further bolster the effectiveness of performance management practices. Policymakers should consider investing in training for public servants and adopting digital tools to streamline processes and improve service delivery.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights, it has several limitations that should be acknowledged. One limitation is the potential for response bias inherent in survey research. Participants may have provided socially desirable answers rather than their true perceptions, which could affect the reliability of the data.

Additionally, the structure and number of survey questions might lead to respondent fatigue, potentially compromising the depth and reliability of their responses.

Future research should aim to explore these dynamics further, perhaps through qualitative methods that can capture the nuanced experiences of public servants. Longitudinal studies could also provide insights into changes in performance management practices over time, particularly in the context of ongoing reforms in local governance.

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Appendix A-1: Survey questionnaire for performance management in the municipalities in the Republic of North Macedonia

Note: *For research purpose, we need your cooperation. The survey is anonymous. Mark or write the answers to each question. Thank you for your cooperation!*

I. Demographic data for respondents

1. Gender a) Male b) Female
2. Age a) <25 b) 25-30 c) 31-35 d) 36-40 e) 41-50 f) 51-55 g) 56-60 h) >61
3. Category of the municipality a) urban b) rural
4. Work position in the municipality a) Managerial b) Non-managerial.
5. Employment status a) Indefinite b) Definite
6. Work experience a) 0-4 years b) 5 to 9 years c) 10 to 14 years d) 15 to 19 years e) 20 to 24 years f) 25 to 29 years g) 30 to 34 years h) more than 35 years

Appendix A-2: Survey Questions related to conducting performance evaluation of employees in the municipalities in the Republic of North Macedonia, including transparency.

Please, answer the following question, with yes, no or don't know.

7. Does your municipality conduct a performance evaluation of employees?
a) Yes b) No c) I don't know
8. Does your municipality carry out self-assessment of the performance of employees?
a) Yes b) No c) I don't know
9. Does your municipality carry out regular online (live broadcast) of the sessions of the council of the municipality?
a) Yes b) No c) I don't know

10. The annual plan and program according to which your municipality works are published and easily accessible to the public?

a) Yes b) No c) I don't know

11. The budget, reports and final accounts of the municipality are publicly announced?

a) Yes b) No c) I don't know

Appendix A-3: Questions for attitudes toward the use of systems for evaluating the performance of employees in the municipalities in the Republic of North Macedonia

Please, express the degree of agreement with each of the statements, namely:

1. Completely disagree 2. Partially disagree 3. Neutral 4. Partially agree 5. Completely agree

12. The budget affects the performance management of employees in the Macedonian municipalities

13. Your municipality has a website and updates it regularly

14. The work goals in your municipality are set reasonably and are realistically achievable within the stipulated time frame

15. Your municipality is currently transparent enough

16. Digitalisation in the municipality can improve the efficiency of the local government

17. The municipality uses advanced GPS digital technologies for monitoring and household use of official vehicles

18. Your municipality is currently digitalized enough and offers services in line with the modern way of life

19. The manager/supervisor should recognize and reward the loyalty and commitment of employees

20. In your municipality, the performance of employees is properly assessed and valued

21. The employees/supervisors in the municipality possess the necessary skills and knowledge to carry out work tasks professionally, efficiently and with quality

22. Your work is properly valued and you are satisfied with the amount of financial compensation (salary) that you receive

23. You are ready and believe that you can put in extra effort if you are properly financially motivated

24. The existing communication between the employee and the superior helps in higher productivity

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25. In your municipality, it is strictly recorded electronically who comes and goes from their workplace
 26. Any unclear problem or challenge should be shared with the manager/mayor
 27. Constant evaluation and trainings help to improve and perfect the work
 28. Extensive evaluation of employees causes job dissatisfaction
 29. I work better when my performance is being evaluated
 30. Employee performance evaluation should be done regularly in a pre-defined period of time
 31. Weekly/monthly reports on the work done can help to motivate employees more
 32. Increasing the budget of the municipalities improves the service at the local level to the citizens of North Macedonia
 33. Good training and communication is the key to greater operational efficiency
 34. The transparency of the municipality affects the service provided by the employees to the citizens
 35. Constant evaluation of work causes stress and anxiety
 36. Digitalisation accelerates the efficiency of employees in providing services
 37. When evaluating performance, the employee's personal characteristics, behaviour and results should be taken into account
 38. Job performance should be used as the basis for rewards and punishments
 39. Innovative solutions should be organized by the mayor for greater motivation and rewards for employees
 40. It is necessary to discuss with the employee the reasons for the poor evaluation results and advice and guidance to improve them
 41. Frequent holding of trainings and lectures helps to improve the performance of employees
 42. Digitalisation has a wide impact on the budgeting of Macedonian municipalities
 43. Digitalisation is directly related to and affects the municipality's transparency, behaviour and results
 44. People are employed in the municipality based on political party affiliation
 45. There are employees in the municipality who receive a salary that they do not work and they should be fired
 46. The municipality has a shortage of staff and more people need to be employed
 47. Privileged persons by supervisors work in the municipality

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48. Does your municipality carry out evaluation of managers by subordinates?
49. Are the results of the evaluation of the employees in the municipality transparently published?

Appendix A-4: Working overtime to implement a project and recommendations

Please answer with short description on these open-ended questions

50. Have you ever worked overtime for the successful implementation of a certain project and were you paid extra by the Municipality for that extra work?
51. Is there something that you would like to add and that you think would help in promoting and improving the status of employees and the services they provide to citizens?

Appendix B-1: Questionnaire for interview with the employees in North Macedonian municipalities

The answers to the questions are completely anonymous, we do not collect personal data and link them to the answers.

1. Identify national and regional standards bodies, laws and regulations that have an impact on PMS (Performance Management System) deployment. Are there laws or rules that impose the use and measurement (evaluation) of the performance of municipal employees?
2. Does your local government carry out employee performance evaluation and how does it organize it?
3. Time / period when you implement PM?
4. Do you have a strategy for implementing PM? What goals and activities do you define?
5. What indicators are used in performance measurement?
6. Do you use a reward method and under what conditions?
7. Costs of implementing PM? Competent bodies, inspection bodies...
8. Do you use training and education training for PM?
9. Previous experiences of implementing PM... When it is introduced...
10. What kinds of challenges and advantages do you face and which can be observed in the implementation of PMS?
11. Is there anything that you would like to add that you think would help promote and improve the status of employees and the services they provide to citizens?